

Effect of Oral Moxonidine in the Attenuation of the Haemodynamic Responses Seen During Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Background: In this study, we wanted to evaluate the effect of orally administered moxonidine in attenuating the hemodynamic responses that occur during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods: This was a hospital based prospective double blinded randomized study conducted among 50 patients underwent elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the Department of General Surgery and Department of Surgical Gastroenterology, in S.C.B. Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, over for a period of one and a half years, from January 2021 to October 2022 after obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethics Committee and written informed consent from the study participants.

Results: The mean pulse rate in the preoperative, at induction, at intubation, before PNP, at 5 min, 10 min, 20 min, 30 min, 40 min, 60 min after PNP, at the end of PNP, extubation was lower in moxonidine group than placebo group. The results were statically significant ($P < 0.05$). The mean systolic blood pressure between moxonidine and placebo at various intervals during the surgery was recorded and the result was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Whereas in comparison of mean diastolic blood pressure between moxonidine and placebo, most of the results were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The use of moxonidine in laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a promising approach in attenuating the hemodynamic response (PR, SBP, DBP and MAP) not only during the operative procedure but also at induction of anaesthesia, endotracheal intubation, recovery from anaesthesia and post-operative period. There were no side effects or deleterious influences on the hepatic, renal and gastro-intestinal function in any of the patients of the moxonidine group in view of its safety profile. Moxonidine is worth considering not only in ASA grade I and II patients but also in ASA grade III patients too because of the stable haemodynamic it ensures when used. As it seems placebo group resulted in a stable hemodynamic (within 10 % of base line) in ASA grade I and II patients. So, 5 – 10 % increase in hemodynamic parameter can be detrimental in ASA III and IV patients.

Keywords: Moxonidine, Haemodynamic, Laparoscopic, Cholecystectomy

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Introduction

No other surgery has been as profoundly affected by the advent of laparoscopy as cholecystectomy has. In fact, laparoscopic cholecystectomy has been instrumental in ushering in the laparoscopic era. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has rapidly become the procedure of choice for routine gallbladder removal and has become the most common major abdominal procedure performed. Laparoscopic surgery is one of the most important diagnostic and therapeutic tools in the present surgical era. Since 1987, when the first laparoscopic cholecystectomy was successfully performed by Phillippe Mouret, this has become the gold standard. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is one of the most commonly undertaken procedures in general surgery, with overall complication rate being less than 1.5 %, and the mortality 3.3 times greater in open cholecystectomy group than laparoscopic cholecystectomy group.[1] The initial driving force behind rapid development of laparoscopic cholecystectomy was patient's demand. Prospective randomized trials were late and largely irrelevant and gained acceptance not through organized and carefully conceived clinical trials but by acclamation.

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy requires pneumoperitoneum and thus routinely requires general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation and intermittent positive pressure ventilation.[2] The pneumoperitoneum created for laparoscopy produces complex physiologic events and changes that make anaesthetic management difficult.[3] The pathophysiologic processes resulting from a pneumoperitoneum are directly related to and have a cause-and-effect relationship to clinical outcomes. These changes include

increase in the heart rate, increase in mean arterial pressure, decrease in cardiac output and increase in systemic vascular resistance which can lead to altered tissue perfusion. Preventing or beneficially modifying these pathophysiologic processes directly affects clinical outcomes. Various techniques and pharmacological agents have been used to counteract these detrimental effects of pneumoperitoneum. These changes though better tolerated in ASA I and II patients can be detrimental in elderly and ASA III patients particularly with compromised cardiovascular system physiology. Various techniques and pharmacological agents have been used to counteract these detrimental effects of pneumoperitoneum. These included gasless laparoscopy,[4,5] uses of β adrenergic blockers,[6] Nitroglycerine,[7] calcium channel blockers and α -2 agonists such as clonidine[8] and dexmedetomidine.[9] The central antihypertensive drug moxonidine, which has a weak affinity for the α 2-adrenoceptor (α 2AR), is generally described as a selective I1-imidazoline receptor (I1R) agonist that lowers blood pressure (BP) by decreasing sympathetic activity within the central nervous system.[10]

It is well known that the rostral ventrolateral medulla (RVLM) plays a critical role in tonic and reflex control of sympathetic outflow and BP.[11] The pre-sympathetic neurons in the RVLM project directly to sympathetic preganglionic neurons in the spinal cord and are recognized as a major target responsible for the action of centrally acting antihypertensive agents such as clonidine and moxonidine.[12,13] Moxonidine causes a decrease in sympathetic nervous

system activity as measured by norepinephrine, and plasma renin activity[14] and, therefore, a decrease in blood pressure. Hemodynamic studies show that moxonidine reduces arterial pressure by lowering systemic vascular resistance while sparing heart rate, cardiac output and stroke volume. In this study, orally administered moxonidine was evaluated in reducing the hemodynamic response that occur during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of the study was to evaluate effect of orally administered moxonidine in attenuating the hemodynamic responses that occur during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital based prospective double blinded randomized study conducted among 50 patients underwent elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the Department of General Surgery and Department of Surgical Gastroenterology, in S.C.B. Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, over for a period of one and a half years, from January 2021 to October 2022 after obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethics Committee and written informed consent from the study participants.

Inclusion Criteria

- Healthy adult patients of ASA physical status I and II of Either sex aged 20 to 60 years,
- Weighing 50 to 90 Kg

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with hypertension, history of cardiac, pulmonary, hepatic or renal disease, psychiatric disorder.
- Patients under drug therapy of beta blockers, methyldopa, and monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitors were excluded from the study.
- Body mass index > 30,
- Patients with the base line heart rate < 60 beats per minute, base line systolic blood pressure < 100 mmHg, ECG abnormalities,
- Patients in whom intubation was thought to be difficult.

Statistical Methods

Data was entered in MS Excel and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Results were presented as tables.

Results

The mean pulse rate in the preoperative, at induction, at intubation, before PNP, at 5 min, 10 min, 20 min, 30 min, 40 min, 60 min after PNP, at the end of PNP, extubation is lower in moxonidine group than placebo group. The results were statically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 1: Comparison of Mean Pulse Rate between Moxonidine and Placebo

Mean Pulse Rate			
	Moxonidine Mean \pm SD	Placebo Mean \pm SD	P Value
Pre op	85.76 + 9.76	98.08 + 8.08	0.0001
At induction	90 + 7.37	95.56 + 7.78	0.01
After intubation	93.6 + 5.6	104.44 + 4.33	0.0001
Before PNP	89.2 + 4.85	99.32 + 5.21	0.0001
5 min after PNP	98.32 + 7.95	106 + 6.80	0.0006
10 min after PNP	90.36 + 4.18	112.76 + 5.91	0.0001
20 min after PNP	87.92 + 4.86	113.1 + 1.6	0.0001
30min after PNP	84.68 + 4.70	110.64 + 4.23	0.0001
40min after PNP	83.08 + 3.45	108 + 4.26	0.0001
60min after PNP	80.56 + 4.30	103.6 + 5.53	0.0001

End of PNP	83.56 + 4.59	100.28 + 4.62	0.0001
Extubation	84.48 + 7.51	101.12 + 8.04	0.0001

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Systolic Blood Pressure between Moxonidine and Placebo

Mean Systolic Blood Pressure			
	Moxonidine Mean \pm SD	Placebo Mean \pm SD	P Value
Pre op	119.20 + 8.63	126.92 + 7.60	0.0016
At induction	123.72 + 6.54	126.48 + 6.58	0.14
After intubation	124.20 + 7.58	130.96 + 3.98	0.0003
Before PNP	124.32 + 7.91	129.12 + 7.03	0.027
5 min after PNP	126.08 + 6.30	141.28 + 4.20	0.0001
10 min after PNP	125.28 + 5.90	134.48 + 2.82	0.0001
20 min after PNP	124.04 + 5.42	132.88 + 3.93	0.0001
30min after PNP	122.44 + 4.80	131.68 + 5.24	0.0001
40min after PNP	122.68 + 6.30	134.72 + 4.50	0.0001
60min after PNP	123.04 + 4.65	134.40 + 4.07	0.0001
End of PNP	122.44 + 3.74	130.84 + 4.38	0.0001
Extubation	122.52 + 4.91	131.12 + 2.88	0.0001

The results of comparing the mean systolic blood pressure between moxonidine and placebo recorded at various intervals during the surgery were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Diastolic Blood Pressure between Moxonidine and Placebo

Mean Diastolic Blood Pressure			
	Moxonidine Mean \pm SD	Placebo Mean \pm SD	P Value
Pre op	77.44 + 6.48	84.76 + 7.13	0.0004
At induction	82.80 + 3.93	82.44 + 6.15	0.8
After intubation	83.20 + 3.88	89.72 + 5.00	0.0001
Before PNP	83.1 + 3.92	84.54 + 6.16	0.13
5 min after PNP	85.08 + 2.94	92.52 + 4.08	0.0001
10 min after PNP	84.60 + 2.65	92.6 + 3.48	0.0001
20 min after PNP	83 + 2.8	90.52 + 4.46	0.0001
30min after PNP	82.24 + 2.28	90.72 + 3.30	0.0001
40min after PNP	81.2 + 3.49	91.84 + 3.31	0.0001
60min after PNP	85.64 + 3.44	89.12 + 3.77	0.0001
End of PNP	86.2 + 4.03	92.6 + 4.91	0.0001
Extubation	83.20 + 3.88	94.4 + 7.18	0.0001

The results of comparing the mean diastolic blood pressure between moxonidine and placebo group recorded at various intervals during the surgery were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Arterial Blood Pressure between Moxonidine and Placebo

Mean Arterial Blood Pressure

	Moxonidine Mean \pm SD	Placebo Mean \pm SD	P Value
Pre op	94.44 + 3.36	98.24 + 4.59	0.0016
At induction	97.72 + 4.42	98.40 + 2.71	0.51
After intubation	97.80 + 3.88	106.24 + 4.22	0.0001
Before PNP	100.28 + 3.58	102.52 + 3.70	0.03
5 min after PNP	98.8 + 4.68	105.12 + 3.3	0.0001
10 min after PNP	96.88 + 4.92	102.20 + 3.89	0.0001
20 min after PNP	95.64 + 5.08	102.44 + 4.94	0.0001
30min after PNP	95.24 + 2.82	103.96 + 3.54	0.0001
40min after PNP	95.24 + 4.16	103.88 + 4.28	0.0001
60min after PNP	92.64 + 4.03	107.16 + 3.73	0.0001
End of PNP	91.76 + 4.19	100.28 + 5.38	0.0001
Extubation	95.16 + 4.24	108.04 + 4.15	0.0001
Comparison of Mean Arterial Blood Pressure between Moxonidine and Placebo			

The above table compares the mean arterial blood pressure recorded at various intervals during the surgery. Most of the results are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

Jean L Joris et al. in 1998 investigated endocrine correlates of the hemodynamic changes induced by carbon dioxide pneumoperitoneum and concluded that vasopressin and catecholamines probably mediate the increase in systemic vascular resistance.

Moxonidine [4-chloro-N-(imidazoline-2-yliden)-6-2-methyl-5-pyrimidineamin] is a centrally active antihypertensive agent that is effective in mild to moderate hypertension and have a favourable adverse effect. Moxonidine stimulates the imidazoline-1 receptors in the ventrolateral area of the medulla oblongata, leads to a decreased sympathetic tone in resistance vessels, the heart, and the kidney. When applied in dosages equipotent to clonidine, its side effects, ie, dry mouth and dizziness, are less pronounced than with the α_2 -receptor agonist clonidine.[15]

A study by Joris J L concluded that vasopressin and catecholamines probably mediate the increase in systemic vascular resistance observed during PNP.

Moxonidine when given before PNP reduces catecholamine release and attenuates hemodynamic changes during Laparoscopy.

In our study the following results are observed.

- There were no significant differences found with respect to age, weight, gender, time between premedication to anaesthetic induction, duration of laryngoscopy and surgical procedure. The anaesthetic technique did not differ among the study groups.
- The preoperative mean pulse rate was lower in the Moxonidine group (85.76 ± 9.76) per min when compared to the placebo group (98.08 ± 0.08) per min; (p value 0.0001). There was no difference in the intubation response with regard to mean pulse rate in both the groups but the rise in the pulse rate after creating pneumoperitoneum was higher in the placebo group whereas the pulse rate was maintained at a stable level in the moxonidine group. The results were statistically significant. ($P < 0.05$).
- The systolic blood pressures in the moxonidine group were on the lower side when compared to the placebo group. The pre op SBP in Moxonidine group (119.20 ± 8.63) mm Hg was

comparable to that of the placebo group (126.92 ± 7.60) mm Hg; (p value 0.0016). Moxonidine group did not show a significant rise in systolic blood pressure post intubation and after creation of pneumoperitoneum. The SBP in the placebo group was fluctuating throughout the procedure; maintaining on the higher side whereas it was maintained at a stable in the moxonidine group. The results were statistically significant. ($P < 0.05$).

- The pre-operative DBP values were lower in the Moxonidine group (77.44 ± 6.48) mmHg than that of the placebo group (84.76 ± 7.13) mmHg; (p value 0.001). Moxonidine group did not show significant rise in DBP post intubation and after creation of pneumoperitoneum. The DBP in the placebo group was fluctuating throughout the procedure, maintaining on the higher side. The intubation and extubation response of DBP were attenuated in the moxonidine group but not in the placebo group. The results were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).
- Moxonidine group did not show significant rise in MAP in post intubation and after creation of pneumoperitoneum. The MAP in the placebo group was on a higher side compared to the moxonidine group; pre op (98.24 ± 4.59 mm Hg vs 94.44 ± 3.36 mm Hg) and the post op MAP (108.04 ± 4.15 vs. 95.16 ± 4.24 mm of Hg). The results were statistically significant. ($P < 0.05$).

In our study, the overall hemodynamic profile was stable in the moxonidine group when compared to the placebo group. The mean pulse rate, SBP, DBP, MAP were stable throughout the procedure in the moxonidine group without any significant fluctuations intra-operatively. The results obtained in our study are consistent with previous study [16,17,18,19] in attenuating

hemodynamic responses to laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Málek J. et al. [19] evaluated the effect of moxonidine 0.3 mg (n = 22) and 0.4 mg (n = 25) p.o. on the attenuation of haemodynamic response during laparoscopic cholecystectomy in comparison with clonidine 150 μ g.i.v. (n = 23) and control group (n = 22). Though Málek J. et al. had concluded that administration of clonidine in premedication before laparoscopic cholecystectomy provides better results; compared to moxonidine we have not done any comparison with clonidine. Only a control group was used for comparison.

As moxonidine has a favourable effect on the metabolic profile in the body, its use in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy is advantageous as most of these patients have some derangement in the metabolic profile with regard to blood sugar levels, lipid profile etc. Moxonidine has edge over other centrally acting antihypertensive like clonidine and dexmedetomidine in avoiding gross sedation. Other adverse effects of clonidine such as dryness of mouth, rebound hypertension are not observed with moxonidine which makes it a more preferable choice.

In our study, hemodynamic profiles were pretty stable throughout the operative procedure requiring very minimal or negligible pharmacological interventions intra-operatively.

Conclusion

The use of moxonidine in laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a promising approach in attenuating the hemodynamic response (PR, SBP, DBP and MAP) not only during the operative procedure but also at induction of anaesthesia, endotracheal intubation, recovery from anaesthesia and post-operative period. There were no side effects or deleterious influences on the

hepatic, renal and gastro-intestinal function in any of the patients of the moxonidine group in view of its safety profile, Moxonidine is worth considering not only in ASA grade I and II patients but also in ASA grade III patients too because of the stable haemodynamic it ensures when used. As it seems placebo group resulted in a stable hemodynamic (within 10 % of base line) in ASA grade I and II patients. So 5 – 10 % increase in hemodynamic parameter can be detrimental in ASA III and IV patients.

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